

Mixed Chelate Complexes of Copper(II)

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Some mixed chelate complexes of Copper(II) of the type $[Cu(dtc)(ox)]$ and $[Cu(\beta, dik)(ox)]$ where dtc =dithiocarbamate, β, dik = β , diketone and ox =oxine have been synthesised and characterised by elemental analyses, molar conductance, room temperature, magnetic moment, infrared and electronic spectral data. The complexes are paramagnetic and non-electrolytic in nature, having presumably square planar geometries.

DIVALENT copper forms several four-coordinated planar complexes both with mono- and bidentate ligands. Dithiocarbamates, β -diketones and oxine are uninegative bidentate ligands having $-SS-$, $-OO-$ and $-ON-$ donor sites. Further it was reported¹ that the antifungal action of dithiocarbamates is enhanced in the presence of cupric ion. Oxine is also known^{2,3} to possess both antifungal and antibacterial properties. Hence it was thought worthwhile to study whether mixed chelate complexes of Copper(II) can be prepared containing these bidentates.

Experimental

Bis diethyl (Et^2 dtc), morpholyl (Morph. dtc) and piperidyl (Pip. dtc) dithiocarbamates of Copper(II) were prepared by known method⁴. *Bis* acetylacetonato ($acac$), benzoylacetonato ($bzac$) and dibenzoylmethenato ($bzbz$) Copper(II) were also prepared as per published method⁵.

Reaction of bis dithiocarbamate Copper(II) with Oxine :

Bis dithiocarbamate Copper(II) compounds were reacted separately with oxine in 1 : 1 molar ratio in chloroform medium. The resulting solution was refluxed for one hour. The separated complexes were suction filtered, washed with ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Reaction of bis β -diketonato Copper(II) with Oxine :—

To a methanolic solution of $Cu(acac)_2$ an ethanolic solution of oxine was added in 1 : 1 molar ratio. The resulting solution was refluxed for one hour and the separated complex was suction filtered, washed with methanol followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*.

In case of $Cu(bzac)_2$ and $Cu(bzbz)_2$, the reaction with oxine in 1 : 1 molar ratio was carried out in chloroform medium. The resulting solution was refluxed for one hour for separating out the

complex which was suction filtered, washed with ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Copper and Sulphur estimated by Standard Methods :

Infrared spectra in the range $5000-650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were recorded on Nujol mulls using Unicam SP 200 double beam spectrophotometer. The magnetic susceptibilities were determined at room temperature on solid specimens using Gouy method. Diamagnetic corrections were made using Pascal's constants. The molar conductance was measured in $10^{-3}M$ acetone solution using Toshniwal conductivity bridge, type CLOIO2 and a dip type cell.

Results and Discussion

The analytical, molar conductance and magnetic susceptibility data are recorded in Table 1. Infrared and electronic spectral data are recorded in Table 2.

All the compounds are non-electrolytes as indicated by the low molar conductance values, (See Table 1). Magnetic susceptibility measurements indicate that all the complexes are paramagnetic with one unpaired electron as expected for a $3d^9$ cupric ion. The values of the magnetic moments for square

TABLE 1—ANALYSES, MELTING POINTS, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC MOMENT VALUES OF MIXED CHELATE COMPLEXES OF Cu(II)

Complexes	Colour	M.P. °C	%Cu Found/ cal	%S Found/ cal	Λ_m (mhos)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
$[Cu(Et_2dte)(OX)]$	Shining black	200	17.52/ 17.87	18.33/ 18.00	0.63	1.86
$[Cu(Morph.dtc)(OX)]$	Brown	280	16.90/ 17.19	17.50/ 17.31	0.65	1.95
$[Cu(Pip.dtc)(OX)]$	Green	222	17.45/ 17.28	17.10/ 17.41	0.60	1.83
$[Cu(acac)(OX)]$	Green	225	20.51/ 20.72	—	0.93	1.86
$[Cu(bzac)(OX)]$	Green	220	16.95/ 17.24	—	0.89	1.83
$[Cu(bzbz)(OX)]$	Green	220	14.50/ 14.75	—	0.82	1.85

TABLE 2—INFRARED AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA (IN cm^{-1}) OF MIXED CHELATE COMPLEXES OF Cu(II)

Complex	dithiocarbamate			Oxine	λ_{max}
	$\nu_{\text{C-N}}$	ν_{CS}	$\nu_{\text{C-S}}$		
[Cu(Et ₂ dte)(OX)]	1510	990	710	1120	16393
[Cu(Morph.dtc)(OX)]	1490	1000	710	1100	16129
[Cu(Pip.dtc)(OX)]	1510	1000	720	1100	16393
	β -diketone		Oxine	λ_{max}	
	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$	$\nu_{\text{C=C}}$			
[Cu(acac)(OX)]	1600	1560	1120	16500	
[Cu(bzac)(OX)]	1600	1580	1100	16500	
[Cu(bzbx)(OX)]	1600	1560	1100	16600	

planar Copper(II) complexes lie in the range 1.83-1.86 B.M.^{6,7}, whereas for tetrahedral configuration, the moments will be larger than 2.0 B.M. In the present case, μ_{eff} values of the complexes suggest square planar structure.

Infrared Spectra :

The relevant infrared absorption bands due to the coordinated chelates in the complexes with their possible assignments are given in Table 2. Many bands due to oxine are found to be overlapping with the bands of dithiocarbamates. However, the most characteristic bands which could be definitely assigned were given in the table. The $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ bands due to dithiocarbamates indicate clearly that they are coordinated to the metal ion through both the sulphur atoms⁹. In the β -diketonato complexes the bands due to $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C=C}}$ were observed in the region 1600 cm^{-1} and 1570 cm^{-1} respectively as expected, indicating the presence of coordinated carbonyl group of β -diketone¹⁰. In addition to the bands cited above, a strong band round about 1100 cm^{-1} was also observed. Charles *et al*¹¹ reported that in several oxine complexes of metals, $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ was observed at 1120 cm^{-1} region, the position of the band slightly varying with the metal. In the present investigation, the invariable presence of strong band at 1100 cm^{-1} definitely indicates the presence of oxine group in the complex.

Electronic Spectra :

Though three transitions $2B_{1g} \rightarrow 2A_{1g}$, $2B_{1g} \rightarrow 2B_{2g}$ and $2B_{1g} \rightarrow 2E_g$ are expected for Copper(II) complexes, they are very close in energy and often give rise to one broad band envelop. Sacconi⁸ and Meek and Ehrhardt¹² have observed that square planar complexes have a complex broad band at relatively

higher frequencies ($16,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The regular tetrahedral complexes of Copper(II) show no d-d absorption bands in the region $10,000$ - $20,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ¹³. The spectra of all the mixed chelate complexes now studied display a broad band around $16,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be assigned to a combination of the two transitions $2B_{1g} \rightarrow 2A_{1g}$ and $2B_{1g} \rightarrow 2E_g$ in D_{4h} symmetry¹⁴. The position of this absorption band ($16,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) is in agreement with those generally observed for planar Copper(II) complexes¹⁵⁻¹⁸.

Thus, the compounds reported now are definitely four-coordinated mixed chelate complexes of Copper(II) with presumably square planar geometry.

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